

Original Research

Visual Marketing and Choice of Academic Service Providers in Cross River State

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Abstract

Scholars have increasingly examined how visual marketing influences consumer buying behaviour, but studies focusing on Cross River State were not found, and the influence of visual marketing is currently underexplored. By adopting the theory of the hierarchy of effects model, this study investigated the influence of visual marketing and the choice of academic service providers. The researchers employed a cross-sectional survey. The researchers employed a convenience sampling technique based on an online questionnaire to collect data from participants. Parents from four selected private nursery schools across the metropolis participated in the study, with a sample size of 446. We tested the collected data using a simple linear regression analysis. Findings showed that visual marketing and its dimensions (image design and colour of the uniform worn) have a significant influence on the choice of academic service providers. Based on the study's findings and conclusion, we recommended that the management of these schools across the metropolis select the best colour for their pupils' uniforms, given the significant influence of colour on the participants.

Keywords: Academic service providers, colour of uniform worn, images design, visual marketing.

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Introduction

In recent years, the educational market in Cross River State has experienced significant growth, leading to a highly dynamic and complex market environment (Usani and Eko, 2021). Numerous marketing forces, such as advertising, packaging designs, branding, social media, and many others, influence the educational sector, contributing to this growth phenomenon (Usani *et al.*, 2021). The urban areas of Cross River State are witnessing a growing competition among academic service providers, a trend that is likely to continue as new private schools emerge. Studies have shown that businesses that are adopting visual marketing are experiencing a significant increase in terms of customer acquisition and loyalty (Kwang, 2019; Etuk, *et al.*, 2022). Scholars such as Krishna and Schwarz (2014) and Nwachukwu and Affen (2023) widely acknowledge the significant impact of visual stimuli on patronage decisions. Sensory marketing aims to attract customers by appealing to their senses, which in turn strengthens their emotional connection to the product and increases the likelihood that they will make a purchase. Sensory marketing covers the various senses of consumers, which has an impact on their perception, evaluation, and actions (Krishna, 2012).

One effective method of eliciting parents' engagement with a certain academic service provider is through the implementation of sensory marketing techniques, such as the use of visual marketing strategies. Visual marketing contributes in a meaningful way to improved student enrollment, parent engagement, and internal employee engagement (Haghigi, *et al.*, 2010). When used as a marketing tool, it can set academic service providers apart from their competitors and drive growth like never before (Singh, 2020). The term "visual marketing" refers to the practice of promoting a product or service through the use of visual elements such as photos, films, and infographics (Nwachukwu and Affen, 2023). Visual marketing seeks to provide maximum experience in a way that takes hold of the attention of the consumer through the use of the eyes as the primary sense (Masai, 2011). Visual perception has a significant impact on how humans act and perceive their environment.

Research on the choice of academic service providers (private secondary school owners) is a valuable endeavour due to the growing prevalence of marketing-oriented practices within the academic sector and the corresponding shift in students' roles from learners to consumers (Chen, 2008). The influential factor of choice frequently influences parents' (consumers') decision to choose a particular academic service provider. The subject area under consideration is commonly referred to as consumer buying behaviour, as described by Kotler and Armstrong (2010). Understanding the consumer's decision-making process can help explain a parent's choice of an academic service provider and its underlying factors. Mogaba (2006) outlines the steps that customers are said to take before making a purchase. The buyer must first recognise a need or problem before beginning with an information search. After then, an evaluation of alternatives to buy, a purchase decision is made after considering the alternative, and finally, a post-purchase evaluation.

Kotler and Armstrong (2010) claim that the consumer's ranking of the alternatives to determine their purchasing intention leads to the purchase choice. Academic service

providers are like other business organisation, seeking customers' satisfaction. According to basic marketing concepts, if these academic providers within Cross River State recognise their customers' needs and wants, meeting them becomes easier. Also, any service provider that seeks to enjoy a competitive edge must respond to customer needs so as to promote satisfaction and secure continuous customer patronage. The intensity of competition has created the need for academic service providers to seek ways of serving their customers better so as to win their patronage.

Visual marketing is a subset of sensory marketing; businesses apply various sensory stimuli in the hopes of optimising customer patronage. This study focuses on the image design and colour of the uniforms worn by these academic providers as dimensions of visual marketing. Existing studies have shown that firms rely on these visual marketing strategies in their efforts to enhance customer patronage (Edim and Inyang, 2022). Researchers have explored studies aimed at determining how visual marketing practices could sustainably enhance customer patronage, given the indispensable need to consistently enhance customer patronage in a dynamic business environment. Nevertheless, researchers have frequently neglected and given lower priority to visual marketing techniques in their studies since they have primarily focused their study efforts on other sensory stimuli (Etuk *et al.*, 2021). As a result, this study aims to investigate two phenomena: visual marketing and the selection of academic service providers. Scholars and consumer behavior researchers worldwide have made significant contributions to the field of sensory marketing and consumer buying behavior, yet there is a dearth of empirical research on the impact of visual marketing as a sensory cue on academic service providers in the Cross River State. Furthermore, the majority of the reviewed studies did not specifically target Cross River State or the selection of academic service providers. In addition, these concepts have not been examined in a collaborative way. Hence, the main aim of this study was to investigate the influence of visual marketing on the choice of academic service providers in Cross River State.

Specifically:

- i. The researchers seek to examine the influence of images design and choice of academic service providers in Cross River State.
- ii. To evaluate the influence of colour of uniform worn on choice of academic service providers in Cross River State.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

An Overview of Visual Marketing

Historically, marketers have employed visual marketing as a means to depict a narrative and establish a profound connection with their target audiences. In the contemporary era characterised by a proliferation of visual stimuli and an incessant influx of information, the significance of visual marketing cannot be overstated. It serves as a pivotal tool for effectively navigating the overwhelming volume of content and leaving a lasting impression on the audience (Al-Alsaggaf and Basaffar, 2022). Through the utilisation of captivating visual elements, organisations have the ability to establish a

robust emotional bond with their target audience, amplify brand awareness, and proficiently communicate their distinctive value propositions (Minocha, 2023). Visual marketing endeavours to provide a memorable and persuasive encounter that resonates with consumers (parents) and motivates them to engage with a particular service provider, whether it is through captivating photos on signboards, visual advertisements, or engaging videos. Masai (2011) averred that visual marketing is a strategic approach that facilitates the connection between products and consumers by employing various visual content such as videos, animations, and images to promote firms products and services. The author further asserts that visual marketing is a strategic practice that involves the skillful presentation of products or services in a visually appealing manner with the intention of capturing the customer's attention and influencing their purchasing behaviour.

According to Usani *et al.* (2016), visual marketing is a strategy that uses visual elements and design to successfully communicate marketing messages. Visual marketing's power stems from the psychological principles that make visual stimuli so persuasive. Minocha (2023) sees the concept of visual marketing as involving the deliberate and planned utilisation of various visual components, including photos, films, graphics, and other visual elements, with the aim of effectively conveying and promoting specific products, brands, or messages. Johnson (2019) sees visual marketing as the strategic utilisation of various visual elements such as photographs, graphics, films, and other forms of visual information in order to promote and advertise a certain product or service. Nwachukwu and Affen (2023) opined that visual marketing encompasses various marketing strategies aimed at engaging the visual sense, such as visual merchandising, visual branding, and other approaches that utilise visual stimuli to capture consumer attention and encourage their patronage of retail establishments, including fast food restaurants.

The arrangement and display of merchandise in retail stores significantly capture the attention of customers. The practice of showcasing items in storefront windows emerged as an initial manifestation of visual marketing displays, with the primary objective of enhancing sales by initially capturing the attention of potential customers through compelling window displays and subsequently through in-store visual merchandising displays. Hendricks (2019), maintained that the notion of visual marketing encompasses the establishment of a correlation between marketing communications and diverse visual components, including images, graphics, infographics, films, logos, signage, and other visual depictions.

Dimensions of Visual Marketing

Images Design

Harnessing the power of images and signboard designs can make a marketing plan more powerful and memorable. The fundamental principle of visual marketing is rooted on the notion that there are instances in which images serve as a more efficacious means of conveying information (Kirby, 2023). The effectiveness of visual marketing is predicated on the innate human inclination towards visual perception. Research suggests

that consumers have a higher capacity to recall information when presented with visual stimuli, such as images, as opposed to textual material.

On the other hand, Kim *et al.* (2012) said that signboards generally provide information about businesses and help consumers make choice on patronising items when consumers visit cities or engage in consumer activities. Consumers accept visually presented information through their eyes. At this time, if the visual parts of the signboard are constructed in agreement with the consumer's visual principles, the consumer at some point acknowledges that the signboard has already been observed and processed for memory. As such, images and signboards are key features of academic service providers and may be one of the most effective ways of providing information (Kim, *et al.*, 2021).

A signboard, according to Manaher (2023), is a form of signage that is generally characterised by its larger dimensions and greater prominence in comparison to other varieties of signs. Specifically engineered to withstand various environmental conditions, signboards commonly use resilient materials like metal or plastic. Graber (2016) demonstrates that visual images and signboards possess the capacity to capture the attention of consumers. According to Myerowitz (2018), an image possesses the ability to elicit human interest through fleeting observation and then create sensory experiences. Images and signboards possess the capacity to effectively communicate dramatic narratives, evoke emotional responses, and depict reality in a manner that surpasses the capabilities of language in isolation (Graber, 2016). In an effort to generate a profound effect, printed images or pictorial images frequently endeavour to evoke captivating visual imagery that resonates with the consumer's memories (Cope *et al.*, 2010). Among the sensory senses of consumers', the reliance on vision is absolute, and visual marketing is generated through the perception of the physical environment of academic service providers' servicescape. Therefore, we formulated the following hypothesis in null form:

H₁: There is no significant influence between images design and choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State.

Colour of Uniform Worn

Visual marketing makes heavy use of colour to sway consumer behaviour, send messages, and elicit desired emotional responses. This means that colour has a far broader function in marketing than simply adding visual appeal to a product. The influence of colour on consumer emotions is significant since it has the ability to evoke a range of affective responses (Małgorzata, 2023). The study of colour psychology is a discipline that examines the ways in which colours can influence consumers' emotions, and behaviours. This field aims to comprehend how specific colours can trigger certain associations in consumers and how they can be utilised in a variety of contexts, such as advertising, interior design, or marketing (Joshi, 2022). Malgorzata (2023) believes that colours are capable of eliciting a vast range of emotions and moods. For instance, warm colours such as red, orange, and yellow are frequently linked with energy and joy, while cooler colours like blue, green, and violet can evoke feelings of calmness and harmony. Selecting the most appropriate colours in visual marketing can effectively convey particular emotions and create the desired ambiance for academic service providers. The

importance of colour and the ways of emotion evoking used in visual marketing is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Showing the meaning of colours and ways of arousing emotion with the selection of colour.

Colour	Characteristics And Emotions
Red	The power of experience and full of life. Ideal for "impulsive" shop-ping. Moreover, it increases the activity and appetite. Often combined with yellow, white or black.
Black	Used for charities, luxury products, exposing sophistication or mystery
Blue	Exposing calm, cool, relief, relaxation. Used in pastel colors to bring lightness.
Dark blue	Associated with professionalism, trust, authority, management. Introducing law and order.
Yellow	Often used as a liaison with other colors. With orange and black- attracts attention. With red - stimulates the appetite. Characterizes those undecided, in the ad it challenges willingness to act and try - hence sometimes used with package products with eg. Fast loans, holidays.
Green	The importance of tone - symbolizes toughness, tenacity, need to recognize. Recommended for use in businesses. In addition, used in products to emphasize vigor, health, activity. The darker tone associated with common sense, rationality.
Violet	Strongly influences the impulsive young consumers. Not often used in business communications.
Orange	The color of joy and vigor. Releases energy, activity, adds strength. Suitable for commercials fruit, emphasizing the positive emotions associated with the use of a particular good or service.
Brown	The color associated with a sense of safety, peace or frustration. It is associated with practicality, tradition, conscientiousness, diligence.
White	Versatile color that is often used in area of Zen with other colors as a contrast. Associated with personality, maturity, independence and purity.
Pink	Gentleness, innocence, girlishness, widely used in products for infants and children.

Source: adopted from Peszko, (2016).

Etuk *et al.*, (2021) concluded that the selection of appropriate colours plays a crucial role in establishing the desired impression that can effectively impact brand and product preferences. From the above discussion, the following hypothesis was formulated.

H₂: Colour of uniform worn does not have significant influence on choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State.

Choice of Academic Service Providers

We use the term "choice of academic service providers" to refer to consumer buying behaviour, as described by Kotler and Armstrong in 2010. Consumer behaviour can be described as a series of acts undertaken by individuals in order to fulfil their genuine

wants, characterised by the pursuit of value (Babin and Harris, 2016). This implies that the decision-making process of purchasing or abstaining from purchasing involves the consideration of genuine thoughts, emotions, and behaviours. Nell (2017) asserts that customers are driven by two fundamental factors while making decisions. Primarily, individuals are motivated by the need to fulfil their internal desires and preferences. Additionally, the presence of multiple alternatives contributes to their motivation. Hence, irrespective of the underlying factors, it is imperative for consumers to engage in decision-making processes regarding the specific category of goods they intend to acquire, possess, and utilise. Parents' or students' decisions involve a complex series of actions in which people interact with one another or behave differently (Kwang, 2019). According to Kotler and Keller (2010), the choice process of parents and pupils may be broken down into five distinct processes.

Theoretical Framework

The study relies on the theoretical framework of the Hierarchy of Effects model, which Lavidge and Steiner proposed in 1961. This theory measures the effectiveness of advertising using a six-step structure that starts with creating awareness and concludes with making a purchase. This model delineates the path that buyers take when exposed to advertising. The concept begins with the awareness stage, in which the customer observes the advertisement and becomes cognizant of it through visual perception. The subsequent stage entails acquiring knowledge, which necessitates becoming acquainted with the advertised product or service. Following that, there is the emotional stage, during which you determine if you have a favourable or unfavourable opinion of the service or product. The consumer will proceed to the next stage, which includes the desire to make a purchase, convincing oneself to make the purchase, and ultimately acquiring the goods or services if they are satisfied with the product. Visual marketing have a crucial role in capturing customers' attention and influencing their purchasing decisions. This concept is directly applicable to our study variable, which focuses on visual marketing methods. This study is based on the hierarchy of effects, which posits that visual marketing, targeting customers' sense of sight, is essential in a successful promotional campaign to gain customers' patronage and loyalty towards a brand's product offering.

Empirical Framework

Numerous empirical studies have examined visual marketing and its underpinnings to influence customers' behaviour. For instance, Al-Alsaggaf and Basaffar (2022) examined how visual marketing affects clothing store purchases. The survey sampled 66 Jeddah retail store customers. A 23-item research questionnaire was given to study participants. They used SPSS to analyse their study data. The researchers analysed the data using simple correlation, partial regression, and stepwise multiple regression. The study found that visual marketing strategies greatly affect Jeddah customers' purchase behaviour.

Similarly, a study conducted by Nwachuckwu and Affen (2023) aimed to examine the influence of visual marketing tactics on consumer engagement within the restaurant industry in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study utilised a quantitative approach, notably employing a cross-sectional survey design. The target demographic for this study was the complete customer base of 377 registered eateries in Rivers State, as recorded in the

Rivers State Yellow Page Directory. Pearson moment correlation coefficient was used to analysed the data collected. The performed research has demonstrated a significant link between the use of visual marketing techniques and multiple indications of client engagement, such as customer patronage, repeat purchases, and recommendations. Hence, the present study has arrived at the conclusion that visual marketing strategies exert a significant influence on customer involvement within the restaurant sector.

Randhawa and Saluja (2017) investigated how visual merchandising affects Punjab residents' impulse purchases. This study used a multi-stage sampling approach to partition Punjab into Malwa, Doaba, and Majha. 450 people were sampled for data collection. The researchers used convenience sampling to choose a population sample. Visual merchandising's effect on impulsive buying was examined using multiple regression analysis. The study found that visual merchandising influences impulsive buying. This shows that visual merchandising informs, reminds, and inspires buyers.

A study of visual displays and sight atmospherics by Nell (2017) examined how sensory surroundings affect consumer purchase behaviour. The study used a qualitative exploratory design. Thematic analysis was used to assess data from two eight-person focus groups. Visual merchandising displays have an unconscious influence on customer behaviour, and although visual display is not the only aspect evaluated when making a purchase, a pleasant ambiance would encourage participants to remain longer and possibly buy. Further, sight atmospherics influenced consumers' conscious or subconscious conduct, which affected how long they spent in an apparel retail store and if they bought anything.

Masai (2011) examined how visual marketing affects music brand recognition in his thesis. The study aimed to assess the perceived contribution of visual marketing to music brand awareness and its effects. A demographically diverse sample of 50 male and female undergraduate students aged 18–24 from the University of Nairobi College Of Humanities and Social Sciences was selected via purposive sampling. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse and interpret the questionnaires. The study's findings demonstrate that visual marketing strategies are widely perceived as the most effective means for consumers to explore and encounter new music.

After conducting a comprehensive analysis of prior studies, we utilised the visual elements of image design and colour of uniforms worn as indicators of visual marketing, while ensuring academic service providers was held as a uni-dimensional construct. This study hypothesised a correlation between visual marketing and the choice of academic service providers, drawing on previous researchers' empirical findings. Figure 1 presents a conceptual model that demonstrates the proposed connection between the variables being studied.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of Visual Marketing and choice of Academic Service Providers.

Research Methodology

The study employed a cross-sectional survey research approach. This facilitated the acquisition of primary data from parents in the selected private schools in Cross River State during a specific time frame. The southern senatorial district of Cross River State, Nigeria, served as the study area. The senatorial district consists of seven local government areas: Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Biase, Akampka, Calabar municipality, Calabar South, and Odukpani. The study area choice became significant due to cost minimization, ease of access, convenience, and the researcher's ability to gather primary data from respondents in the study area. Significantly, the absence of prior research on visual marketing and the specific selection of academic service providers within the city made the specific geographical location pertinent. The study's target population consists of parents whose children attend the selected private nursery schools in Cross River State. We selected four private nursery schools from the senatorial district: Gemhill All Stars Academic, Top Exquisite International Schools, Emerald Field Schools, and Mary-Gold International. The researchers identified this population by accessing parent records from the four selected schools during the research period. In the four selected private schools, the population of parents was 446. Since the population was less than 500, we chose 446 as our sample size. The breakdown is as follows in Table 2.

Table 2. population of parents in the four selected private nursery schools in Cross River State

Name Of Schools	Population	Percentages (%)
Emerald Field Schools	115	26
Gemhill All Stars Academic	107	24
Top Exquisite International Schools	126	28
Mary-Gold International	98	22
Total	446	100%

Sampling Technique

The current study employed a convenient sampling technique, which is the most common type of non-probability sampling. Convenient sampling is an approach of gathering samples by taking samples that are conveniently located around a location or online.

Source of Data Collection/Scaling

Data for this research was collected through primary sources using an online research questionnaire developed by the researcher and titled “Visual marketing and choice of academic service providers in Cross River State. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A consists of respondent demographics, while Section B consists of the main variables used in the study. The questionnaire consists of multiple-choice questions with the predictor and criterion variables measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree, agree, undecided, strongly disagree, and disagree with values of 4, 3, 0, 2, and 1, respectively. However, in administering the research instrument, a link was sent to the proprietors of these selected private nursery schools to be shared on their parents WhatsApp platforms.

Reliability Coefficient of the Study Variables

The Cronbach alpha was used as a reliability parameter to determine the internal consistency of the research questions in the study. This is a concept that stresses the consistency between the items in the questionnaire and is the most widely used objective for measuring the reliability of a study instrument when working with Likert scales. An acceptable limit could be between 0.7 and 0.8. Hence, a Cronbach alpha of above 0.7 indicates internal consistency of items and can be relied upon to explain the influence of visual marketing and the choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State. The outputs of the reliability test for the study were all above the 0.7 benchmark, as shown in Table 3., so we proceeded with the analysis.

Table 3. Computed Reliability Coefficient of the study Variables

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	no. of items
Images and Signboards	0.714	3
Colour Design of Uniform	0.735	3
Customer patronage	0.813	3

Method Data Analysis Technique

The analysis of the respondents' personal data involved the utilisation of simple frequency percentages and a frequency distribution table. In order to assess the degree of influence between visual marketing variables (X1, X2) and the choice of academic service providers (Y), the simple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the two hypotheses. All hypotheses were evaluated at a significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected when the probability value is shown to be less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Data Presentation

Three weeks after the online response solicitation date, 322 accurately filled-out copies of the questionnaire proved useful and valid for analysis. This represents 72% of the total 446 relevant questionnaire copies. We excluded the remaining 124 respondents, representing 28%, from the analysis because they did not complete the online survey. Table 4 reveals the analysis of demographic variables.

Table 4. Demographic Data of the Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
<u>AGE</u>		
18-29	85	15.8
30-39	152	22.4
40 and Above	40	18.3
Total	322	100.0
<u>GENDER</u>		
Male	142	44.1
Female	180	55.9
Total	322	100.0
<u>MARITAL STATUS</u>		
Single Parent	98	30.3
Married	228	69.7
Total	322	100.0
<u>EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION</u>		
SSCE OR Below	3	0.9
NCE/ND	35	11.1
HND/B.Sc	126	39
B.SC and Above	130	40
Others	28	9
Total	322	100.0
<u>EMPLOYMENT STATUS</u>		
Civil Servant	132	41
Self Employed	107	33
Unemployed/students	25	8
Others	58	18
Total	322	100.0

According to the analysis results in Table 4.1, for age grouping, 18–29 constituted 15.8%, 30-39 were 22.4% and 40 and above constituted 18.3%. Male and female respondents constituted 44.1% and 55.9%, respectively. For marital status, single parents and married constituted 30.3% and 69.7%, respectively. Out of 322 respondents, 0.9% were SSCE holders. 11.1% were NCE or ND holders. 39% were HND or BSC holders. Holders of BSC and above were 40%. 9% of respondents did not mention any other

certificates. In addition, 41% of respondents were civil servants. 33% were self-employed. Unemployed students were 8%, while others constituted 18%.

Test of Hypothesis

H₁: There is no significant influence between image design and choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State.

Table 5. Results of Regression Analysis on the Influence of Image Design and Choice of Academic Service Providers in Cross River State

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.202 ^a	.041	.038	2.45949
a. Predictors: (Constant), Image design				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	82.070	1	82.070	13.567	.000 ^b
	Residual	1935.706	320	6.049		
	Total	2017.776	321			
a. Dependent Variable: Choice of academic providers						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Image design						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.990	.727		12.359	.000
	Image	.221	.060	.202	3.683	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Choice of academic providers						

Results of the simple linear regression analysis show that the independent variables, images design, accounted for approximately 4.1% of the variation in choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, with a regression coefficient of $R^2 = 0.041$. This means that images design as predictor of visual marketing were accountable for 4.1% of the changes in choice of academic service providers, while 95.9% of the changes in the dependent variable could be attributed to other factors not considered in the study's model.

Results on the table also indicate that the influence between the independent variables was significant but weak according to the $R = .202$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.038$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a weak explanatory power of the dependent variable. In addition, the F-ratio = 13.567 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that images design significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (choice of academic service providers). This result, as presented in the coefficient table, can be

interpreted that every unit change in the independent variable will lead to an increase in the dependent variable, holding all other factors constant. As represented in the resulting econometric model,

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

$$\text{Cap} = a_0 + \beta_1 \text{Ios} + e$$

Thus, the resulting simple linear regression model is presented as:

$$\text{Cap} = 8.990 + 0.221 \text{Img}$$

H₂: Colour of uniform worn does not have significant influence on choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State.

Table 5. Results of Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.376 ^a	.142	.139	2.32659
a. Predictors: (Constant), Colour				

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	285.613	1	285.613	52.764	.000 ^b
	Residual	1732.163	320	5.413		
	Total	2017.776	321			
a. Dependent Variable: Choice						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Colour						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.464	.587		12.720	.000
	Colour	.356	.049	.376	7.264	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Choice						

Results of Hypothesis 2 show that the coefficient of determination at R^2 of 0.142 implies that the independent variable (colour of uniform design) accounted for 14.2% of the variation in choice of academic service providers. In addition, the significant F-ratio at $F = 52.764$, $P < 0.000$, suggests that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that the independent variable significantly predicted the dependent variable. To ascertain the importance of the independent variable in determining the degree of change in the dependent variable, the beta coefficients for the variable, colour of uniform design X_2 , had a statistically significant standardised coefficient of ($\beta = 0.356$, S.E. = 0.049, $t = 7.264$, $p = 0.000$ $p < 0.05$), revealing a significant weak influence on choice of academic service providers. This finding can be

interpreted as saying that every 1 unit change in the colour of the uniform worn will lead to 0.356 changes in the choice of academic service providers. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence on the colour of the uniform worn and the choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Cross River State.

As represented in the resulting econometric model,

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$\text{Cap} = a_0 + \beta_2 \text{Cou} + e$$

Thus, the resulting simple linear regression model is presented as:

$$\text{Cap} = 7.464 + 0.356 \text{Csw}$$

Discussion of Findings

The present study attempted to investigate the influence of visual marketing and its selected dimensions on the choice of academic service providers. First, among the study sample, the proposed model explains 4.1% of the variance in choice of academic service providers, that is, $R^2 = 0.041$ with a regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.221$. This indicates that the design of images and signboards has a significant influence on the choice of academic service providers. Our findings are consistent with most previous research on the need for firms to integrate visual elements into their marketing strategies. The results also strengthen the reports of Al-Alsaggaf and Basaffar (2022), Randhawa and Saluja (2017), and Masai (2011), who in their studies at different geographical location and time found that visual elements (such as images designs) are positively and significantly related to patronage of firms' products. Taking visual image for instance, Al-Alsaggaf and Basaffar (2022) assert that images hold the highest significance among all visual elements. Pictures and drawings attract the customers' attention, who notices all the visual alterations very quickly. The vast majority of customers are of the opinion that the images have an impact on the purchasing process.

The results of the second hypothesis demonstrate that the colour of the uniform was found to have a significant influence on the choice of academic service providers, with a regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.356$. The findings justify visual marketing dimensions (such as the colour of the uniform design) as a strategy for marketing to enhance consumer (parents) patronage behaviour towards the choice of academic service providers in Cross River State, Nigeria. Hence, this finding agrees with Nwachuckwu and Affen (2023), and Nell (2017); they also demonstrate that colour design is capable of creating positive behaviour that can stimulate patronage of firms, products, and services. In their study, Nwachuckwu and Affen (2023), who used the senses to affect perception, judgement, and behaviour, discovered that colour can influence consumer patronage level. The school's wall colour, and classroom should be painted to align with the colours used on the uniform and other branding touch points. Studies have shown that colours influence patronage hence, the colours chosen should fit the school concept. It should be pleasing to the eyes and induce a welcoming feeling. It should enhance the atmosphere with a proper lighting theme, creating a positive perception in consumers' minds (Nell, 2017).

Conclusion and Business Implications

The results of this study make it clear that visual marketing significantly influences consumers' (parents) decisions about academic service providers. This is supported by the influence of visual marketing elements on academic choice, including images, signage design, and uniform colour. This indicates that in creating an academic environment, visual marketing is seen as a crucial marketing strategy. The study provides some useful insight for practitioners in the fields of marketing and management of private schools. From the findings of the study, it is evident that visual marketing plays an efficient and effective role in enhancing patronage behaviour. Images convey complex concepts in a brief manner, and visual elements like colour can improve and stimulate the desire of parents to express various feelings and outlooks.

Further studies are required to cover some of the shortfalls in the present study. For instance, studies that might explore the impact of sensory marketing and the choice of academic service providers are recommended, as the present study could not take this approach in considering all dimensions. Again, further studies are encouraged to cover the other states and their metropolises in Nigeria that were not captured in the present study. And finally, studies and ongoing studies are required to adopt the regression analytical method to see if their regression coefficient output will be stronger than the output of this present study. This will help to strengthen the findings of the study in the context of Cross River State, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions, we recommend the following:

- i. Academic service providers or school board management should continuously improve the graphic designs of their images on their signboards and banners in order to create an emotional appeal in the minds of customers (parents).
- ii. The management of these schools throughout the metropolis and the state should make sure they choose the best uniform color for their pupils, as the study period revealed that color had a significant influence on the participants.

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